

Medicine Use in Lactation and Application of the Information, Motivation, and Behaviour Skills Model among Breastfeeding Women in Kampala, Uganda

Pre-and post-questionnaire to assess the Information, Motivation and Behaviour model constructs. (v1.0 14-08-2023)

Demographics

- i) Maternal age:
- ii) Number of children:
- iii) Age of Infant (s).....
- iv) Highest level of education
 - a) College/university
 - b) Secondary
 - c) Primary
 - d)No education
- v) Occupation
 - a) Civil servant
 - b) Business person
 - c) Peasant
 - d) Housewife
- vi) Medicine use during breastfeeding in the last 6 months.
 - a) Did not receive any medicines
 - b) Received prescribed medicines
 - c) Received non-prescribed medicines
 - d) Received herbal/natural remedies
 - e) Did not take any herbal/Natural medicines
- vii) If taking any medicines: Which medication are you currently taking and for how long?

Drug	Period
Anti-tuberculosis drugs	
Malaria drugs	
Antiretroviral	
Anti-hypertensives	
Diabetic drug	
Isoniazid	
Others: Specify	
Not sure	

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A. Information construct to assess knowledge on medicine use during breastfeeding

Instructions: Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements by ticking the box that best represents your opinion.

NO	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	Use of medicines while breastfeeding can protect the baby from acquiring the disease					
2.	I am aware that some medicines may affect my baby while I breastfeed					
3.	I have enough information about using medicines safely while breastfeeding.					
4	I know where to find information about medicines and breastfeeding.					
5	It is ok to take medicines without any advice from a healthcare provider					
6	It is not necessary to inform the prescriber about the medicines you are using during breastfeeding					
7	I prefer to have three or more drugs prescribed per consultation					
8	Alcohol and smoking cannot have any effect on my breastfeeding baby					
9	I talk to my family or friends about medicines I can use while breastfeeding					
10	I can take my herbal medicines without informing the healthcare provider					
	score					
	Total score					

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B. Motivation construct to assess the attitudes and beliefs on medicine use during breastfeeding.

Instructions: Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements by ticking the box that best represents your opinion

No	Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1	All medicines can be used during breastfeeding without any concern					
2	All medicines can be harmful to the infant					
3	Breastmilk is not safe for my infant while taking medicines					
4	I can stop breastfeeding while on medication					
5	I use medicines for any disease during breastfeeding to protect the infant					
6	Consultation with your doctor while breastfeeding and taking medicines cannot reduce unnecessary harms					
7	I can permanently stop breastfeeding to complete the treatment					
8	Breastfeeding women should use natural remedies without the advice of a doctor					
9	I have to consult my spouse, parents, friends, and relatives before I take any medicine during breastfeeding					
10	I can disrupt my breastfeeding schedule when taking medicines					
scores						
Total scores						

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C. Behaviour construct to assess medicine use practices.

Instructions: Please indicate how often you engage in the following practices by ticking the box that best represents your frequency.

No	Item	Scale				
		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1.	Use of herbs instead of Western medicine during breastfeeding					
2.	Sharing drugs with my infant					
3.	Following dosage instructions for medications prescribed to me while breastfeeding					
4.	Adjusting my breastfeeding schedule (e.g., timing of feeds or stopping breastfeeding) based on my medication use.					
5.	Using over-the-counter medicines while breastfeeding without consulting a healthcare provider					
6.	Use of left-over medicines while breastfeeding					
7.	Seeking additional information (e.g., online resources, pharmacy, healthcare provider, reading the labels on medications) before taking medicines.					
8.	Discussing my breastfeeding status with my healthcare provider before taking prescribed medications					
9.	Storage of medicines under the bed, open cupboard, bag, and dining table.					
10.	Keeping a record of medications I take while breastfeeding.					
	Scores					
	Total					